

An Acculturation Review of the Population Phenomenon in the Formation of Cultural and Religious Traditions in Yogyakarta

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Abstract

This article discusses the Acculturation Review of the Immigrant Population Phenomenon, in the Formation of Cultural and Religious Traditions in Yogyakarta. Given that the wealth of deep cultural and religious traditions in Yogyakarta, not only becomes the center of attention in the context of social change. However, the presence of immigrant populations in the city not only brings new challenges, but also opens up opportunities for acculturation. This article focuses on the significant influence of immigrant populations on the transformation of long-established cultural traditions and religious practices. Through a qualitative approach, the research applies in-depth interviews and participatory observation in several immigrant communities, to explore the interactions that occur between immigrants and local people. The results show that immigrant populations not only adopt local traditions, but also actively contribute to enriching and modifying cultural and religious practices. This acculturation process creates a unique blend of cultural elements and generates new dynamics in the social life of the people of Yogyakarta. As such, this research provides important insights into intercultural interactions and how these relationships shape collective identity in a multicultural society. The findings provide a foundation for further understanding of how diversity can be managed and celebrated, and how the process of acculturation can be a bridge to create harmony in a diverse society.

Keywords: Religion, Acculturation, Immigrant Population, Cultural Traditions, Yogyakarta

Abstrak

Yogyakarta, dengan kekayaan tradisi budaya dan agama yang mendalam, menjadi pusat perhatian dalam konteks perubahan sosial yang kompleks. Kehadiran populasi imigran di kota ini tidak hanya membawa tantangan baru, tetapi juga membuka peluang untuk akulturasi yang menguntungkan. Dalam penelitian ini, kami berfokus pada pengaruh signifikan dari populasi imigran terhadap transformasi tradisi budaya dan praktik keagamaan yang telah lama ada. Melalui pendekatan kualitatif, penelitian ini menerapkan wawancara mendalam dan observasi partisipatif di beberapa komunitas imigran, untuk menggali interaksi yang terjadi antara imigran dan masyarakat lokal. Hasil yang diperoleh menunjukkan bahwa populasi imigran tidak hanya mengadopsi tradisi lokal, tetapi juga aktif berkontribusi dalam memperkaya dan memodifikasi praktik budaya

serta agama. Proses akulturasi ini menciptakan perpaduan elemen budaya yang unik dan menghasilkan dinamika baru dalam kehidupan sosial masyarakat Yogyakarta. Dengan demikian, penelitian ini memberikan wawasan penting mengenai interaksi antarbudaya dan bagaimana hubungan ini membentuk identitas kolektif dalam masyarakat yang multikultural. Temuan ini menjadi landasan bagi pemahaman lebih lanjut tentang bagaimana keberagaman dapat dikelola dan dirayakan, serta bagaimana proses akulturasi dapat menjadi jembatan untuk menciptakan harmoni dalam masyarakat yang beragam.

Kata Kunci: Agama, Akulturasi, Populasi Imigran, Tradisi Budaya, Yogyakarta

Introduction

The phenomenon of the presence of immigrants in various parts of the world has also been able to increase global mobility triggered by various factors, such as developments in technology, communication and transportation that allow people to move places more easily and quickly.¹ This phenomenon not only reflects significant demographic shifts, but also creates complex interactions between different cultures that may not have interacted with each other before. In Indonesia, particularly Yogyakarta, which is known as a center of culture and education, the city is often a destination for various groups of immigrants, both from other parts of Indonesia and from outside countries with diverse cultural backgrounds.

Yogyakarta, with its characteristics of rich cultural heritage, history and unique traditions, attracts those seeking new opportunities in education, economy and social life.² The presence of these immigrant groups has a significant impact on the social, cultural and religious dynamics of the area, creating a situation where local communities must adapt and interact with the new elements introduced by immigrants.³ On the one hand, interactions between immigrant populations and local communities can enrich cultural traditions, creating an inclusive and dynamic atmosphere that facilitates the exchange of ideas and practices.

For example, immigrants often bring their own traditions, languages and religious practices, which then interact with existing local traditions. This process of interaction produces not only new forms of art and cuisine, but also religious practices that reflect the fusion of two or more cultures. In this context, we can

¹ Muhammad Fauzan Alamari, "Imigran Dan Masalah Integrasi Sosial," *Dinamika Global: Jurnal Ilmu Hubungan Internasional* 5, no. 02 (2020): 254–277.

² Yohanes Primus Supriono, *Ensiklopedia The Heritage Of Batik, Identitas Pemersatu Kebanggaan Bangsa* (Penerbit Andi, 2024).

³ Fadhilah N U R Rohmah, "Wij-Samenleving 2015-2018 Sebagai Upaya Integrasi Imigran Di Rotterdam Belanda" (UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta, 2019).

see how cultural festivals in Yogyakarta are increasingly diverse, featuring elements from different traditions and creating a richer experience for the community.

This confirms that the presence of immigrants not only adds diversity, but also contributes to the formation of a more complex and layered collective identity of the people of Yogyakarta. As such, the immigration phenomenon is an integral part of a broader social process that influences the way people interact and understand each other in a changing world.

However, on the other hand, this phenomenon can also lead to identity conflicts and significant challenges in maintaining existing traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation. Local communities may feel threatened by the changes brought by immigrants, often resulting in social tensions and even open conflict. Uncertainty about their cultural identity and fear of losing traditions that have become an integral part of daily life can create a deep sense of discontent among some community members.⁴ Feelings of alienation and loss can grow, especially among those who highly value their cultural heritage and want to see those traditions kept alive without outside influence. In this context, it is important to deeply understand the dynamics of interaction between immigrant communities and local people, in order to create solutions that embrace diversity and promote constructive intercultural dialogue. This dialogue should not only involve community leaders, but also include voices from different walks of life, including those who feel marginalized. With an inclusive approach, it is hoped that common ground can be found that respects local values while still opening up space for new, positive influences.

The presence of immigrants in Yogyakarta is not only a challenge to be faced, but also a valuable opportunity to enrich the social and cultural life of the region.⁵ This opportunity must be managed wisely through policies that support intercultural integration and collaboration, so that peace and harmony can be maintained amidst diversity. An emphasis on multicultural education and programs that encourage positive interactions between groups will be crucial in creating a society of mutual respect and understanding. With the right measures in place, Yogyakarta can be a living example of how diversity can be managed constructively, making it a force that strengthens the collective identity of the community.

The urgency of this research lies in the pressing need to understand how the presence of immigrant populations significantly affects cultural traditions and

⁴ Anastasia Wiwik Swastiwi, *Globalisasi Dan Media: Konvergensi Budaya Dan Komunikasi* (PT Indonesia Delapan Kreasi Nusa, 2024).

⁵ Anastasia Wiwik Swastiwi, *Globalisasi Dan Media: Konvergensi Budaya Dan Komunikasi* (PT Indonesia Delapan Kreasi Nusa, 2024).

religious practices in Yogyakarta, a city known as a cultural and educational center in Indonesia. In the context of rapidly growing globalization, where geographical and cultural boundaries are becoming increasingly blurred, interactions between different ethnic and cultural groups are becoming increasingly complex, and Yogyakarta is no exception. As a city rich in cultural heritage, encompassing a wide range of traditions, arts, and religions, Yogyakarta faces significant challenges in maintaining a balance between maintaining local traditions that have existed for centuries and dealing with new influences brought by immigrants who come from diverse backgrounds.

This immigrant influence often creates a situation where local communities have to adapt and respond to changes, both in terms of everyday cultural practices and in spiritual and religious contexts.⁶ In this process, local communities may find themselves faced with a difficult choice: either to maintain their existing traditions, or to open up to new elements that can enrich their cultural experience. Therefore, this study aims to explore in depth the acculturation process that takes place between immigrant populations and local communities, and to examine the impact of this process on the cultural identity and religious practices of the people of Yogyakarta.

Through a comprehensive approach, this research will not only provide insights into how intercultural interactions take place, but will also highlight the challenges and opportunities that arise as a result of such acculturation.⁷ By understanding how immigrants contribute to the cultural and spiritual transformation of Yogyakarta, we can identify new patterns in social and religious practices that may not have been observed before. This research is expected to provide valuable recommendations for policymakers, academics, and the general public, in order to design strategies that support harmonious and mutually beneficial integration between local and immigrant communities. As such, the results of this research are expected to strengthen the socio-cultural foundations of Yogyakarta in the face of increasingly complex future challenges.

By understanding these acculturation processes, it is hoped that a clearer picture can be achieved of how cultural identities are formed and evolve in a multicultural context, where elements from different cultures interact and influence each other. This research will also make a significant contribution to the development of social and cultural theories relating to intercultural interaction, as well as provide new insights into how these processes can affect people's daily

⁶ Jurna Petri Roszi and Mutia Mutia, "Akulturasi Nilai-Nilai Budaya Lokal Dan Keagamaan Dan Pengaruhnya Terhadap Perilaku-Perilaku Sosial," *FOKUS Jurnal Kajian Keislaman Dan Kemasyarakatan* 3, no. 2 (2018): 171.

⁷ Muhammad Andre and Surya Atmanegara, "Memahami Identitas Budaya Melalui Lensa Sastra: Eksplorasi Humaniora Dalam Era Globalisasi," *MOUSE JURNAL HUMANIORA* 1, no. 2 (2024): 40–44.

lives.

Through an in-depth analysis of the social dynamics at play, this research aims to produce recommendations that will benefit the management of cultural diversity not only in Yogyakarta, but also in other regions facing similar challenges. In addition, the results of this research are expected to assist communities, policy makers and academics in formulating strategies that support intercultural harmony and collaboration amidst ongoing social change. By providing a solid foundation for understanding intercultural interactions, this research will enable policymakers to design more effective programs and policies to manage diversity and promote social inclusion. On the other hand, people can gain a better understanding of the values of the various cultures around them, thus creating a more tolerant and respectful environment.⁸

More than simply analyzing the influence of immigrants on local communities, this research also seeks to explore the potential synergies that can arise from such interactions. Thus, it is hoped that the results of this research will not only be a valuable source of information, but will also inspire collective actions that facilitate the strengthening of diverse cultural identities and develop a sense of belonging among different communities. In an era of ever-evolving globalization, this understanding is becoming increasingly important for creating societies that are not only diverse, but also harmonious and sustainable.

The rationale for this research is based on a number of previous studies that have shown that acculturation can produce significant changes in multicultural societies.⁹ These studies provide valuable insights into the dynamics of intercultural interaction and how the acculturation process can affect various aspects of social and cultural life. However, there is still a lack of research that specifically examines the context of Yogyakarta, a city with a unique culture and rich history.

Therefore, the focus of this research is to answer important questions: How do immigrant populations influence cultural and religious traditions in Yogyakarta? By answering this question, it is hoped that this research can make a meaningful contribution to the understanding of cultural interaction in a broader context. This research will delve deeper into how the presence of immigrants not only affects existing cultural and religious practices, but also how immigrants contribute to the formation of new identities amidst existing diversity.

Furthermore, the results of this study are expected to offer a richer and more comprehensive perspective on the acculturation process in Yogyakarta, as well as

⁸ Muhammad Mona Adha and Erwin Susanto, "Kekuatan Nilai-Nilai Pancasila Dalam Membangun Kepribadian Masyarakat Indonesia," *Al-Adabiya: Jurnal Kebudayaan dan Keagamaan* 15, no. 01 (2020): 121–138.

⁹ Abdullah Idi, *Konflik Etno Religius Di Asia Tenggara* (Lkis Pelangi Aksara, 2018).

provide relevant information for policy makers and the community. As such, this research will not only enrich the existing literature on acculturation, but will also be a useful reference source for understanding the challenges and opportunities that society faces in the face of ongoing social change. In the midst of the increasingly complex phenomenon of globalization, a deep understanding of intercultural interactions in Yogyakarta will be crucial for creating strategies that support harmonious and sustainable social integration.¹⁰

Research Method

In this study, a qualitative approach was used to explore in depth the influence of immigrant populations on cultural and religious traditions in Yogyakarta.¹¹ This research method was chosen because it allows researchers to understand complex social and cultural contexts and interactions between individuals and groups holistically. With this approach, researchers can explore nuances that may not be expressed through quantitative methods, such as the feelings, experiences, and views of individuals regarding the changes that occur due to the presence of immigrants. Through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions and participatory observation, this research aims to gain richer insights into how local people respond to new cultural influences, as well as how immigrants adapt and interact with existing traditions.¹² This qualitative approach also allowed the researcher to capture the personal stories and unique perspectives of various parties from both the local community and immigrants, all of which contributed to a more comprehensive picture of the dynamics of intercultural interaction in Yogyakarta.

This research is expected to provide a deeper understanding of the complex and diverse process of acculturation, and document how the influence of immigrant populations not only shapes religious traditions and practices, but also affects the social identity of the people of Yogyakarta. This method helps researchers to explore topics flexibly, providing space for informants to share their experiences and perspectives in depth. In addition to interviews, participatory observations were also conducted to gain a richer context of intercultural interactions in the daily lives of the people of Yogyakarta. Furthermore, data obtained from interviews and observations will be recorded and analyzed using a thematic analysis approach. This process involves categorizing

¹⁰ Ines Tasya Jadidah et al., “Analisis Pengaruh Arus Globalisasi Terhadap Budaya Lokal (Indonesia),” *Academy of Social Science and Global Citizenship Journal* 3, no. 2 (2023): 40–47.

¹¹ Akbar Iskandar et al., *Dasar Metode Penelitian* (Yayasan Cendekiawan Inovasi Digital Indonesia, 2023).

¹² Muhammad Najib Husein, Herman La Ode, and Ibrahim Cecep, “Pengantar Penelitian Sosial” (n.d.).

information based on emerging themes and patterns, allowing the researcher to draw relevant conclusions regarding the influence of immigrant populations on cultural and religious traditions in Yogyakarta. These data collection procedures were designed to ensure that the research could provide a comprehensive and in-depth picture of the dynamics of intercultural interactions, and how acculturation processes take place in complex contexts.¹³ As such, the results of the research are expected to make a significant contribution to academic understanding and social practice in Yogyakarta.

The analytical technique used in this study is thematic analysis, an approach that allows researchers to identify, analyze and report on patterns (themes) that emerge from the collected data.¹⁴ The reference criteria or standards used in this study refer to existing acculturation theories, such as social contact theory and cultural integration models, as well as previous studies on relevant cultural interactions. By using this theoretical framework, the researcher can assess and interpret the data in a more systematic way, as well as compare the findings of this study with the results of previous studies. Thus, the thematic analysis not only provides a clearer picture of the acculturation process, but also allows the researcher to relate the findings to the wider literature and contribute to a deeper understanding of cultural interaction.¹⁵

It is hoped that this research can produce a comprehensive picture of the influence of immigration in the multicultural context of Yogyakarta. This includes identifying key themes that emerge from such interactions, such as influences on art, language, religious rituals and social norms. The research will also explore the challenges faced by both groups in maintaining their cultural identities, as well as the opportunities that arise from intercultural collaboration. Thus, the results of this research are expected to provide not only academic insights, but also practical information for communities and policy makers in managing cultural diversity in Yogyakarta. This research aims to support the development of strategies that promote intercultural harmony and openness, so that people can coexist with mutual respect and understanding.

Results and Discussion

Immigrants in Yogyakarta have had a significant impact on the cultural traditions and religious practices of the local community, creating a dynamic

¹³ Ramadhan Syahputra, "Kebijakan Migrasi Dan Implikasinya Terhadap Integrasi Sosial," *literacy notes* 1, no. 2 (2023).

¹⁴ S E Nartin et al., *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif* (Cendikia Mulia Mandiri, 2024).

¹⁵ Husna Ul Nisa, "Analisis Bibliometrik: Trend Topik Penelitian Pada Program Studi Sejarah Dan Kebudayaan Islam Di UIN Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh" (Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-raniry, 2025).

atmosphere that marks the interaction between the two groups.¹⁶ Interviews with informants revealed that interactions between immigrants and local communities tend to result in a form of acculturation that successfully bridges existing cultural differences.

One clear example of this phenomenon can be seen in certain cultural celebrations, such as art festivals and religious holidays. In these contexts, elements of immigrant traditions such as music, dance and cuisine are integrated into local practices, creating experiences that not only celebrate each other's cultural heritage, but also enrich the meaning of these celebrations. For example, in the celebration of Chinese New Year, local people of Yogyakarta not only witness lion and lion dance performances that originate from Chinese culture, but also combine them with local traditions such as gamelan and regional dances. This creates an inclusive atmosphere, where everyone, immigrants and locals alike, can participate and celebrate together, thus strengthening the sense of community and mutual respect.

Moreover, the integration of these cultural elements also contributes to the development of a new identity that reflects the diversity of Yogyakarta as a multicultural city.¹⁷ Through this collaboration, immigrants and local people learn and understand each other's values, customs and beliefs, which in turn has the potential to reduce stereotypes and prejudices that often arise between different groups.

The impact brought by immigrants is not only seen in changes to religious traditions and practices, but also in the creation of a more open and mutually supportive social space.¹⁸ This shows that acculturation is not just a process of adaptation, but also an opportunity to create synergies that enrich the cultural life of Yogyakarta as a whole.¹⁹ One of the main findings of this research is that immigrants not only accept local cultural values, but also actively influence religious practices in Yogyakarta. In participatory observations conducted at various religious events, it was clear that some immigrant communities, such as

¹⁶ Ade Fakhri Kurniawan, Arif Rahman, and A Falikh Alhaq, *Muslim Clicktivism, Pergeseran Otoritas, Dan Diskursus Tradisi Lokal Di Kalangan Anak Muda Banten Dan Yogyakarta* (3M Media Karya, 2020).

¹⁷ Muhammad Ridha Iswardhana et al., "Menggalang Perspektif Masyarakat Keberagaman Etnis Di Yogyakarta Dalam Upaya Memperkuat Integrasi Nasional," *Jurnal Abdi Masyarakat Multidisiplin* 3, no. 2 (2024): 62–68.

¹⁸ Galant Nanta Adhitya et al., "Telaah Ranah Muslimah Mengejawantah Akidah Islamiah Study of the Realm of Muslim Women Embodying Islamic Faith," in *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Universitas Respati Yogyakarta Vol*, vol. 5, 2023.

¹⁹ Uskuri Lailal Munna and Lutfiah Ayundasari, "Islam Kejawan: Lahirnya Akulturasi Islam Dengan Budaya Jawa Di Yogyakarta," *Jurnal Integrasi Dan Harmoni Inovatif Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial* 1, no. 3 (2021): 317–325.

those of Chinese and Arab ethnicity, adopted local religious rituals and customs, while retaining elements of their own distinctive traditions.

For example, in celebrating Eid al-Fitr, immigrant Muslim communities often participate in local traditions such as visiting each other and giving food to neighbors, which is a common practice in Yogyakarta society. However, they also add distinctive elements to their traditions, such as the presentation of certain dishes that have special meaning to their community. This not only enriches their spiritual experience, but also strengthens the relationship with the local community. On the other hand, observations also show that religious practices among local communities have become more dynamic as a result of these interactions.²⁰ For example, some mosques in Yogyakarta have started to organize interfaith activities involving immigrants, where interfaith dialogue and cultural exchange are part of the routine. This indicates adaptation and inclusiveness in religious practices that may have previously been more rigid.

This mix creates a unique atmosphere, where religious practices are no longer static, but become more adaptive to the social changes taking place.²¹ Locals and immigrants learn from each other, integrating new elements into existing practices, resulting in new forms that reflect the cultural diversity of Yogyakarta.

Figure 1. Overlay Visualization

²⁰ H M Ridwan Lubis, *Sosiologi Agama: Memahami Perkembangan Agama Dalam Interaksi Islam* (Kencana, 2017).

²¹ Agus Suryono, *Teori Dan Strategi Perubahan Sosial* (Bumi Aksara, 2019).

The findings of this study confirm that acculturation in religious contexts is not merely transactional, where elements of culture and religious practice are superficially exchanged. Rather, it is transformational, where interactions can change and reshape the way individuals and communities understand and practice their faith. This creates space for the development of new, more inclusive and diverse identities, which in turn strengthens social cohesion in a multicultural society.

In the context of Yogyakarta, this research shows that interactions between immigrants and local communities can make a positive contribution to the dynamics of religious life. The exchange of thoughts, practices and values between different groups creates an environment where diversity is perceived as a valuable asset rather than a threat.²² Yogyakarta is thus an interesting example for the study of cultural interaction, which can serve as a reference for other cities that face similar challenges in managing community diversity.²³ Through this understanding, we can see how acculturation can play a role in creating a harmonious society, where each individual feels accepted and valued, while contributing to the enrichment of existing religious traditions and practices.

This finding is in line with Berry's (1997) theory of acculturation, which states that interactions between two cultures can produce new cultural forms without losing the identity of each group's origin. In the context of Yogyakarta, this phenomenon is particularly evident among the various immigrant communities who come from different cultural backgrounds, such as Chinese, Arab and Indian. Many immigrants strive to maintain their traditions of origin, such as holiday celebrations, religious rituals and social practices, while also adapting to local values.²⁴ For example, the Chinese community in Yogyakarta celebrates Chinese New Year with great fanfare, but they also integrate elements of local culture, such as inviting neighbors to share the typical food served in the celebration. This not only strengthens intercultural relations, but also creates a distinctive atmosphere of mutual respect.

On the other hand, immigrants from the Arab community often hold recitations and religious events at the mosque, but they are also open to

²² Ahmad Tsarwat and Mohd Arifullah, "RESPONS ATAS ORIENTALISME DI TANAH AIR: Antara Konservatisme, Liberalisme Dan Moderat," *TAJDID: Jurnal Ilmu Ushuluddin* 23, no. 1 (2024): 258–288.

²³ Laksmi Widyawati, "Fenomena Budaya Pop Dalam Ruang Publik Kota Yogyakarta," *Jurnal KaLIBRASI: Karya Lintas Ilmu Bidang Rekayasa Arsitektur, Sipil, Industri* 2, no. 2 (2019): 72–86.

²⁴ Chandra Halim, *Dinamika Etos Kerja Masyarakat Tionghoa Yogyakarta* (Sanata Dharma University Press, 2021).

participating in local festivals and social activities involving the local community.²⁵ They adapt some local practices, such as the way food is served, while still maintaining their own cooking traditions and specialties. This process creates a new identity rooted in two different cultures, where elements from the home culture and the local culture complement each other. This is seen in everyday life, where the language, food and dress of each group begin to reflect a fusion of old and new traditions. Moreover, the findings also show that acculturation not only results in complex identities, but also enriches the social and spiritual experiences of the people of Yogyakarta as a whole. By maintaining an identity of origin while adopting local values, immigrants contribute to the formation of a more tolerant and multicultural society. Overall, this study emphasizes the importance of understanding acculturation as a dynamic and mutually beneficial process, where each group can learn and develop from each other without losing their identity. It provides a relevant example for other cities facing similar challenges in dealing with cultural diversity.

Furthermore, the results show that this acculturation process is not without its challenges. One of the main challenges that arises is identity conflict, where some members of the local community feel threatened by the changes brought by immigrants. This feeling often arises when local traditions and values are perceived to be displaced or forgotten, creating tension between the desire to maintain cultural identity and the need to adapt to the presence of a new culture. This resistance can take many forms, such as rejection of new cultural practices that are perceived as foreign, as well as skepticism towards the good intentions of immigrants. Some members of the local community may feel that the presence of immigrants threatens the continuity of their traditions, which have existed for many years.²⁶ This can lead to polarization within the community, where cultural differences become a source of conflict rather than a uniting force.

However, on the whole, the interactions resulted in more collaboration and mutual understanding.²⁷ In many cases, individuals from both groups begin to realize that cultural diversity can be a source of strength rather than a threat.²⁸ For example, through joint activities such as cultural festivals, art exhibitions or cross-community religious events, local people and immigrants can communicate and

²⁵ Khansa Aura Dhiya, "Peran Produser Pada Proses Produksi Film Dokumenter Ncik: Fihi Ma Fihi" (2024).

²⁶ sofiatul Mudhakiroh, "Formulasi Kebijakan Terhadap Imigran Gelap Dalam Hubungan Kedaulatan Negara" (Universitas Islam Sultan Agung Semarang, 2024).

²⁷ Eko Saputro, "Komunikasi Antarbudaya Etnis Lokal Dengan Etnis Pendatang: Studi Kasus Mahasiswa/I Fakultas Adab Dan Ilmu Budaya Uin Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta" (2019).

²⁸ Stephanus Djunatan, "Menghadapi Keragaman Di Indonesia Melalui Konsep Masyarakat Interkultural," *Focus* 4, no. 1 (2023): 71–80.

share experiences that enrich each other's perspectives.²⁹ This process creates space for constructive intercultural dialogue, allowing each group to listen to and understand the views and customs of the other. As a result, many collaborative initiatives have emerged from these interactions, such as mixed arts groups, cultural exchange programs and social activities that involve all parties. This shows that despite the challenges, there is also great potential for building bridges between different cultures.

Therefore, this research not only answers the problem of the influence of immigrant populations on cultural traditions and religious practices in Yogyakarta, but also emphasizes the importance of intercultural dialogue in building a harmonious society. This dialog is key to overcoming tensions and creating stronger bonds between communities, as well as helping to create an inclusive and respectful society.³⁰ This research provides valuable insights into how societies can thrive in diversity, and how positive acculturation processes can contribute to overall social well-being.

Figure 2. Density Visualization

The findings in this study make a significant contribution to the development of acculturation theory, confirming that the acculturation process is not linear or simple. Rather, it is heavily influenced by the specific social and cultural context of each region. The research summarizes the understanding that acculturation is not a uniform journey; rather, it involves a complex interaction

²⁹ Nurul Akhmad, *Ensiklopedia Keragaman Budaya* (Alprin, 2020).

³⁰ Muhamad Nurul Fajri, "Pola Komunikasi Efektif Dalam Moderasi Beragama: Membangun Dialog Harmonis," *Al-Tsiqoh: Jurnal Ekonomi dan Dakwah Islam* 8, no. 1 (2023): 13–33.

between various interrelated factors.

These factors include the history of migration that flows through generations, the social dynamics that develop in the community, and the economic conditions that affect the relationship between immigrants and local residents. For example, in the context of Yogyakarta, the diverse cultural backgrounds immigrants from different ethnicities and traditions and the local community's openness to change are key elements in shaping the experience of acculturation.³¹ This creates an environment rich in cultural interaction, where elements from different cultures blend together, forming a new identity that reflects diversity.³² As such, this research opens up new insights into how acculturation occurs in unique contexts, providing a clearer picture of the dynamics at play in a multicultural society such as Yogyakarta.

The findings also suggest that external factors, such as government policies and community support, can influence the success of the acculturation process. For example, policies that support the social and economic integration of immigrants can create an environment more conducive to intercultural collaboration. Conversely, exclusionary or discriminatory policies can exacerbate identity conflicts and resistance, hindering a positive acculturation process.³³ In addition, this study opens up room for further research into the mechanisms and factors that influence acculturation in other contexts. By considering different variables, such as the types of cultures involved, economic backgrounds and education levels, future research could provide a more in-depth picture of how acculturation takes place in other places, both within and outside Indonesia.³⁴

This explains the importance of acculturation studies in large cities with diverse immigrant populations. By examining urban contexts, we can gain a deeper understanding of the influence of urban environments on intercultural interactions. In this case, factors such as access to resources, government policies and social networks contribute significantly to shaping the relationship between immigrants and local residents. For example, access to education, employment and health services can affect immigrants' ability to integrate into the community. Government policies, such as integration and social support programs, also play an important role in creating an inclusive environment. In addition, social networks formed among individuals from different backgrounds can strengthen a sense of community and mutual understanding.

³¹ Diana Ariswanti Triningtyas, *Konseling Lintas Budaya* (CV. Ae Media Grafika, 2019)

³² M Si Nursilah et al., *Seni Dan Identitas Budaya Di Indonesia* (Takaza Innovatix Labs, 2024).

³³ Rd Heri Solehudin, *Pengembangan Instrumen Penelitian: Analisis Kebijakan Komunitas Perkotaan Dalam Perspektif Interseksional* (Kaizen Media Publishing, 2024).

³⁴ H Dadang Supardan, *Pengantar Ilmu Sosial: Sebuah Kajian Pendekatan Struktural* (Bumi Aksara, 2024).

community activities that encourage direct interaction between different groups. In addition, it is important for researchers to pay attention to the specific context in which acculturation takes place, including the social, economic and political factors that can affect the dynamics of intercultural relations. With an in-depth understanding of the context, the strategies formulated can be more targeted and effective in reducing conflict and increasing collaboration between immigrants and local communities.³⁷

Through a holistic and community-based approach, it is hoped that this research can contribute to the creation of a more harmonious and highly competitive society, where diversity is not only seen as a challenge, but also as a source of strength that can improve the quality of life of all community members. Thus, the lessons learned from this research can be applied not only in Yogyakarta, but also in other regions in Indonesia and around the world that face similar issues in dealing with cultural diversity.

Conclusion

In this study, it was found that the immigrant population in Yogyakarta has a significant influence on cultural traditions and religious practices, which is reflected in the acculturation process that combines elements from both different cultures. The results show that the interaction between immigrants and local communities not only enriches existing cultural traditions, but also creates new dynamics in religious practices that may have previously been invisible. In other words, the presence of immigrants is not only an additional factor in cultural diversity, but also serves as a driver of change that generates new forms of religious traditions and practices that respond to the challenges of the times. These findings reinforce acculturation theory, which emphasizes that cultural interactions can produce new identities that reflect the diversity that exists in society. This process not only demonstrates how cultural elements influence each other, but also shows that acculturation is a complex and multidimensional process, involving adaptation and negotiation of identities among different groups. The novelty of this research lies in the in-depth understanding of how the acculturation process takes place in the context of Yogyakarta, which is an area with a unique cultural richness, including strong local traditions and diverse immigrant cultural backgrounds.

As a suggestion, practical activities such as intercultural dialogues and collaborative events can be implemented to strengthen the relationship between immigrants and local communities, thereby creating space for the exchange of ideas and experiences that enrich both parties. For example, organizing cultural

³⁷ Siti Nurjanah Ahmad et al., *Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Melalui Lembaga Sosial Desa* (Tohar Media, 2024).

festivals involving art performances, culinary delights and panel discussions can be an effective platform to celebrate diversity while building better understanding between groups. In addition, further research is recommended to explore the factors that influence acculturation in other regions, as well as its impact on cultural identity in a multicultural society. This research could include a variety of social and geographical contexts to provide a more comprehensive picture of how acculturation occurs and how this process can be optimized to support social cohesion and intercultural harmony. As such, the results of this research not only contribute to the field of acculturation studies, but also offer practical insights that can be used to design policies and programs that support social integration in increasingly diverse societies.

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